

On the Source-Filter Model of the Vocal Tract

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ABSTRACT

Models of the vocal tract that have a source followed by a linear filter have been of great practical use in Recognition, Compression, Synthesis, etc. Improvements have generally been in the direction of more accurate derivation of parameters. Such refinements now only marginally improve performance, probably because it is linearity, not accuracy of parameters, that is wrong. Inadequacy of the linear model is discussed in this paper, and a simple non-linear model with spring-loaded walls is described.

THE LINEAR FILTER MODEL

The source-filter theory of speech (vowel) production, in particular the LPC or Acoustic Tube model, has been of great practical value in speech applications, e.g. Compression, Synthesis, and Recognition. It may be, however, that all the good that can be wrung out of the linear model has now been attained. More accurate estimates of the parameters of the model are not yielding better results.

It is surely not surprising that a plateau of sorts has been reached, since the source-filter theory in general, and the all-pole model in particular, are surely wrong. For example, measurements made by Teager [1] show that the vocal-tract airflow assumptions necessary to the source-filter theory are unwarranted. Flow is not planar, and velocity waves in different parts of the vocal tract often bear little resemblance to each other or to the output.

The hard-walled-acoustic-tube vocal tract that underlies Linear Prediction Coding (LPC) can be shown to be inadequate, in the following way: when no energy is entering the system, the output of a k -section tube at time n is

$$S_n = \sum_{i=1}^k P_i S_{n-i}$$

where P is the LPC polynomial (see e.g. [2]). That is, the output is a pure recursive sequence of span k . Equivalently, the acoustic tube has an all-pole transfer function, and the signal is a sum of damped sinusoids (whose

frequencies and bandwidths are determined by the positions of the poles in the complex plane, and by the sampling rate). See e.g. [3] for a discussion.

If speech were the output of such a tube, then during the closed-glottis portion of a pitch epoch, speech would be a pure recursion. This means that speech itself, during the closed-glottis period, is (almost) exactly the sum of damped sinusoids, signals of fixed frequency and bandwidth. Thus if we do LPC on speech during the closed-glottis period, the frequencies of the poles recovered during that period should be constant.

Fig. 1 Waveform and LPC pole frequencies (hz) for the vowel /AA/

Figure 1 shows that for real speech, this is not true. The figure shows what happens to the frequencies of the poles recovered by LPC over stretches quite short compared to a pitch period. The abscissa is time in samples (10kc sampling). At the top of the figure is shown some speech (the vowel /AA/). At every sample time a 10-coefficient LPC was done over the next 40 samples of speech, and the frequencies of the poles of the LPC polynomial are plotted vertically at that sample time. Where the window includes the 'pitch-pulse', LPC cannot be expected to model the speech well, and it is not surprising that the poles jump about.

Fig. 2 Waveform and LPC pole frequencies (hz) for a synthetic vowel made from a hard-walled tube

However while the window is sliding through the closed-glottis portion, the poles should not wander. That they do is clear evidence that speech is not created by a hard-walled acoustic tube.

Figure 2 shows LPC poles recovered from a signal that is the output of a hard-walled acoustic tube. A computer simulation of such a tube was made, using the model suggested by Wakita [2], pulsed at realistic pitch intervals. Again the output signal is shown at the top, and the pole positions are plotted at each sample time. When the LPC window does not include the input pulse, the recovered pole frequencies are quite steady (as indeed the arithmetic says they must be).

Figures 3 and 4 show two more speech signals analyzed similarly (the vowels are /EE/ and /UW/). LPC poles are seen to be anything but stationary.

That the phenomenon is not an artifact of the LPC process can be seen by doing a similar thing using a broad (short-time-constant) filter. From the same stretch of speech used in Figure 1, a spectrum was created by passing the speech through a set of 300-hz (digital) filters, and the peaks of this spectrum were found. In Figure 5 the positions of these peaks are shown at each sample time. Peaks are seen to wander just like LPC poles.

The situation is not much better if speech is generated by a tube whose transfer function has zeros as well as poles. The sample $S(n)$ is then a function of (say) m previous input samples as well as k previous output samples, so the portion of the pitch period over which LPC does not model well is lengthened by m , leaving a shortened but still substantial 'closed-glottis' period.

Fig. 3 Waveform and LPC pole frequencies (hz) for the vowel /EE/

Fig. 4 Waveform and LPC pole frequencies (hz) for the vowel /UW/

Fig. 5 Waveform and spectral peak frequencies (hz) for the vowel /AA/

These facts are not new; the figures are a redo of some made by the author 10 years ago. Such results must be known to many researchers, although they seem not to have been published. Nevertheless, there appears to be a continuing search for ever more accurate derivations of the parameters of an incorrect (linear, acoustic tube) model of the vocal tract, and very little effort to produce a (simple) modification of the model that can account for some of the observed anomalies. There is modeling work going on, but it seems to be focusing on the interaction between the super- and sub-glottal cavities, rather than on the properties of the vocal tract.

A NON-LINEAR FILTER MODEL

If linear models are inadequate, we must try non-linear ones. It would seem desirable to try a model that is 'close' to linear, both because it might make calculations easy and because linear is already very good. There is really no hint from physiology as to what kind of mild non-linearity will be most fruitful. Thus, the particular model considered here is intriguing, but not compelling. It departs from the acoustic tube model in just one respect: the sections of the tube are not hard-walled, but spring-loaded. That is, each section is thought of as having a (cylindrical) wall of specified mass per unit area, whose radius obeys Hooke's law (in response to internal pressure). This is like the model proposed by Sondhi [4] except that while his walls yield, they do not actually move; he incorporates the average effect of wall motion.

Lurie [5] shows that the moving-wall situation complicates the partial differential equations very little, namely

$$\frac{\partial(V/A)}{\partial t} + (1/\rho_0) \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + (k_s) \frac{\partial(pA)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial A}{\partial t} = 0$$

where

$V(x,t)$ = volume velocity

$A(x,t)$ = area

$p(x,t)$ = pressure (above atmospheric)

ρ_0 = equilibrium air density

$k_s = 1/(\rho_0 c^2)$, where c = speed of sound

For a uniform tube, a further approximation gives

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = 0$$

$$A \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + k_s A \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial A}{\partial t} = 0$$

The 'traveling-wave' solution of these equations is

$$u(x,t) = f(t - \frac{x}{c}) + b(t - \frac{L-x}{c})$$

$$p(x,t) = \rho_0 c [f(t - \frac{x}{c}) + b(t - \frac{L-x}{c}) - \ln A(t)]$$

This can be incorporated into the LPC synthesis model used by Wakita [2], which is open at the lips and has no reflection at the glottis. The FORTRAN realization of one 'step' of this model is:

Forward and backward waves:

$$F(I) = .5*(U(I)/ZA(I) + P(I)/RHOC - C*ALOG(A(I)/ZA(I))) \text{ for } I=1 \text{ to } K$$

$$B(I-1) = .5*(U(I)/ZA(I-1) - P(I)/RHOC + C*ALOG(A(I-1)/ZA(I-1))) \text{ for } I=2 \text{ to } K$$

$$B(K) = .5*(UL/ZA(K) + C*ALOG(A(K)/ZA(K)))$$

where $U(I)$ and $P(I)$ are velocity and pressure in the I th section, $ZA(I)$ is the area of the I th section at the last step, and $RHOC = \rho_0 c$.

To update the pressure and volume velocity:

$$U(1) = (A(1)/(A0+A(1)))*UG +$$

$$2*(A0/(A0+A(1)))*B(1)$$

$$P(1) = RHOC*(U(1)/A(1) - 2*B(1)) \text{ and}$$

$$U(I) = 2*A(I)*A(I-1)*(F(I-1) + B(I))/$$

$$(A(I-1)+A(I)) \text{ for } I=2 \text{ to } K$$

$$P(I) = 2*RHOC*(A(I-1)*F(I-1) - A(I)*B(I))/$$

$$(A(I-1)+A(I)) \text{ for } I=2 \text{ to } K$$

$$UL = 2*A(K)*F(K)$$

where $A0$ is the (arbitrary) area of the 0th section, UG is the (inserted) volume velocity at the glottis, and UL is the (observed) volume velocity at the lips.

These equations apply to any model in which areas change from one sample time to the next. In the spring-loaded-section model, the areas are updated by the allowing the radius of a (circular) section to vary according to the action of a spring whose parameters have some basis in physiological reality. The equation of motion ($F=ma$) of a section radius is

$$MASS*R'' = P - MECHR*R' - STIF*(R-R0)$$

where $MASS$, $MECHR$, and $STIF$ are mass, mechanical resistance, and stiffness per unit surface area, and $R0$ is the rest radius of the section. The natural frequency and time constant of the spring are:

$$FNAT = \text{SQRT}(STIF/MASS)$$

$$TAU = 2*MASS/MECHR$$

Letting $QF = (2\pi FNAT/FSMP)**2$, the equation for updating the section radius is

$$R_{NEW} = 2R - ZR + F1 - F2 - F3$$

R is the radius at the last update
 ZR is the radius at the previous update
 RNEW is the new radius
 F1 is the effect of air pressure P
 $F1 = P * QF / STIF$
 F2 is the effect of spring tension
 $F2 = QF * (R - R0)$
 F3 is the effect of mechanical resistance
 $F3 = 2 * (R - ZR) / (TAU * FSMP)$

Using this model, speech was generated starting with areas that are reasonable for some vowel and inserting a pitch pulse (by making UG non-zero) at reasonable intervals. Realistic values of FNAT (50) and TAU (.005) were obtained from Fant [6] and Sondhi [4]. A typical waveform is shown in Figure 6, which also shows the pole frequencies as recovered by LPC. The poles are seen to wander in somewhat the same way as they do in real speech.

A remarkable property of this model is the small amount of wall vibration needed to make a large perceived difference in output sound. Forming a 'vowel' from a hard-walled tube, and then allowing the walls of this same tube to vibrate, one gets two very different vowel sounds despite the fact that all sections vary in size (vibrate) less than .003 of their original size.

Fig. 6 Waveform and LPC pole frequencies (hz) for a synthetic vowel made from a tube with spring-loaded sections.

SUMMARY

The linear model of the vocal tract is far enough from being correct that further search for more accurate parameters of such a model may be fruitless. LPC poles are not constant during the closed-glottis portion of voiced speech. (No conjecture is made as to what physical phenomenon is causing this. The word 'formant' has not been used so far in this paper.) A model is described that is 'close' to linear, but does allow poles to wander. Whether the departure from linearity is a realistic one, or is in a fruitful direction, has yet to be determined.

REFERENCES

- [1] H.M. Teager, Some Observations on Oral Air Flow During Phonation, IEEE Trans. Acoust, Speech and Sig. Proc., Vol. ASSP-28, No. 5, Oct. 1980
- [2] H. Wakita, Direct Estimation of Vocal Tract Shape by Inverse Filtering of Acoustic Speech Waveforms, IEEE Trans. Audio Electroacoust., Vol. AU-21, pp 417-424, Oct. 1973
- [3] J. Makhoul, Linear Prediction: A Tutorial Review, Proc. IEEE, Vol. 63, Apr. 1975
- [4] M.M. Sondhi, Model for Wave Propagation in a Lossy Vocal Tract, Jour. Acoust. Soc. Amer. Vol. 55, May 1974
- [5] J.B. Lurie, Notes on Physics of Sound Propagation in the Vocal Tract, IDA-CRD Expository Report No. 20
- [6] G. Fant, Private Communication